

Can we leverage data sharing benefits to increase the adoption of smart farming technologies?

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Abstract

Smart farming practices provide decision-making support for farmers facing economic, social, and environmental challenges. However, the adoption of smart farming remains low in many areas due to the perceived costs, required skills, and hesitations about sharing agricultural data. While many studies have examined the factors influencing smart farming adoption in different agricultural contexts, none have specifically reviewed the motivators and obstacles of agri-data sharing within smart farming. This research aimed to identify and classify the primary drivers and barriers for agri-data sharing among stakeholders by examining existing literature. A Systematic Literature Review was conducted using the PRISMA 2020 methodology, initially identifying 491 papers from Scopus and Web of Science and narrowing down to 34 empirical and 25 non-empirical papers for final assessment. This paper presents the main findings from the 34 empirical studies. Factors affecting the willingness and ability to engage in agricultural data sharing were categorized into socio-economic, systemic, technical, and legal categories. The most prominent drivers for agri-data sharing were socio-economic and systemic, mentioned in 65% and 59% of the empirical papers, respectively. Technical factors were the most common barriers, discussed in 68% of the literature. Key enablers for data sharing included perceived knowledge gain for better decision-making, trust and collaboration across the agri-value chain, practical usage, and clear data sovereignty. Major concerns included a lack of understanding of the purpose and benefits of data sharing, mistrust about who benefits from the data, data privacy and security issues, and unclear data ownership and right of uses. The findings from this study will inform research efforts across the EU to promote the benefits of agri-data sharing and increase the adoption of smart farming technologies.

Keywords: agri-data sharing, smart farming, drivers, barriers, trust

1. Introduction

Farmers worldwide are in a challenging situation: to produce enough for a growing population, decrease their environmental impact, meet consumer and political demands for responsible practices, navigate increasingly adverse and volatile weather, and ensure the survival of their farming operations. Despite these overwhelming challenges, new technologies providing high-quality information can assist farmers in making critical decisions and increasing efficiencies. Over the past three decades, smart farming practices have been developed to address many economic, social, and environmental challenges in agriculture (Fragomeli et al., 2024). Smart farming practices can help reduce inputs and maximise outputs (Wolfert et al., 2017), streamline on-farm processes and redistribute labour needs (Jerhamre et al., 2022), and use resources more sustainably, such as through precision irrigation and targeted pesticide application (Jakku et al., 2019; van Evert et al., 2017).

Data are central to all smart farming processes and management decisions. These data are collected from farms via sensors, machines, drones, or satellites, and from the value chain tracking consumption, prices, input supplies, and energy use (Klerkx et al., 2019). By processing and interpreting these data, farmers can make better decisions at both the farm and value-chain levels (van der Burg et al., 2020). To fully realise the benefits of optimized production, enhanced sustainability, and risk mitigation, these data must be shared. This involves farmers sharing their data with stakeholders such as farm advisory services, ag-tech companies, research institutions, and government agencies. However, data sharing is a complex socio-technical process that is hampered by stakeholder concerns over data privacy, interoperability, unclear governance, and mistrust about who benefits from the shared data (Wiseman et al., 2019).

Whereas trust in smart farming adoption studies is centred on trust in the technology, such as whether the equipment gathers accurate data, trust is discussed very differently in agri-data sharing research. Issues with

trust in data sharing stem from stakeholders' (primarily farmers') perceptions of what will happen to their data once shared, including who will use it for what purpose, and potential repercussions. Some believe trust can be ensured through policies, codes of conduct, and regulation; however, van der Burg et al. (2021) argue that such measures can only help maintain trust previously built through relationships. This review highlights that socio-economic, systemic, technical, and legal factors intersect to influence trust in data sharing.

Numerous studies have identified agri-data sharing as a factor affecting smart farming adoption (Drewry et al., 2019; Jerhamre et al., 2022), but few have focused on it specifically. Previous reviews have examined the technical or privacy aspects of big data in agriculture (Amiri-Zarandi et al., 2022; Kamilaris et al., 2017), only the barriers to data sharing in digital agriculture (Eastwood et al., 2023; Šestak & Copot, 2023), or specific technologies like blockchain (Akella et al., 2023). However, to the best of our knowledge, no reviews have comprehensively explored the motivations and obstacles of agri-data sharing. This research aims to identify and classify the key drivers and barriers for agri-data sharing across stakeholders by reviewing existing literature. Our paper fills the gap with a review of the most prominent factors influencing data sharing in the agri-value chain identified in 34 empirical studies.

2. Materials and Methods

This article forms part of a comprehensive Systematic Literature Review (SLR) recently conducted by Sullivan et al. (2024) using the PRISMA 2020 methodology. This review presents the main findings from the empirical papers identified in the original systematic review. Empirical studies gather and analyse data as evidence, and include both qualitative (e.g., interview) and quantitative (e.g., survey) measurements.

2.1. Identification criteria and screening process

The original search was conducted on February 15, 2024, and utilised Scopus and Web of Science. The search query employed a combination of keywords and their synonyms based on previous reviews (Da Silveira et al., 2021; Gemtou et al., 2024) and was selected after testing several combinations of search terms. The final query used was:

("smart farm*" OR "smart agricult*" OR "precision agricult*" OR "precision farm*" OR "digital agricult*" OR "digital farm*" OR "data-driven agricult*" OR "agriculture 4.0") AND ("data shar*" OR "agri-data" OR "agricult* data" OR "farm* data" OR "sharing data" OR "data exchange" OR "data access" OR "data governance" OR "data privacy" OR "data ownership" OR "data sovereignty" OR trust OR "information sharing") AND (factor* OR barrier* OR deter* OR obstacle* OR limit* OR prevent* OR discourag* OR driver OR motivat* OR encourag* OR attitud* OR perspective OR adopt*)

The keywords were searched within titles, abstracts, and keyword lists. The search was limited to journal articles and conference papers written in English. The search resulted in 491 studies eligible for screening. After removing duplicates, the number of articles was reduced from 489 to 353. The initial screening was conducted by reading titles and abstracts of the 353 papers to make sure the papers fell within the scope of the review. This step removed 227 records. The remaining 126 papers were then screened by reading the full text to determine if they met the following inclusion criteria: (i) Original research (not a review paper); (ii) Study related to digital agriculture; (iii) Discussed a driver or barrier for agricultural data sharing; and (iv) Available for download as full text. This second screening resulted in 32 empirical and 24 non-empirical papers. Two additional empirical papers were added from outside of the query because they were commonly referenced. This resulted in a final number of 34 empirical studies to be analysed for this review.

2.2. Data extraction and analysis

Driver and barrier categories were established based on existing literature (Gemtou et al., 2024; Rozenstein et al., 2024) to analyse results and identify the most prominent factors affecting agricultural data sharing. The four main categories used were: (i) socio-economic factors; (ii) systemic factors; (iii) technical factors; and (iv) legal factors. Data were extracted manually and recorded in a spreadsheet after reading each article. When discussed in the main body of a paper, details of the driver or barrier were recorded in the appropriate category. In this way, the number of papers that addressed the four main drivers or barriers was calculated. Factors discussed were further analysed by assigning them into four or five sub-categories per main category. The frequency of a sub-category was determined by summing the number of times the sub-category was marked across the set of papers. This review presents the two most prominent drivers and barriers per category, while all the sub-categories recorded are discussed in Sullivan et al. (2024).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. General overview of selected articles

A total of 34 empirical studies published from 2011 to 2024 were analysed for this review. Data sharing is a recent area of research, with 90% of the articles published since 2019. Other reviews have noted a recent surge in social and behavioural science studies related to smart farming, particularly from 2018 onwards (Klerkx et al., 2019; McGrath et al., 2023). The high number of publications in 2019 is attributed to a special issue of *Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences* focused on social science within smart farming. Agri-data sharing was found to be only a component of the research or discussion in many of the papers (e.g., data sharing as a factor influencing the adoption of smart farming). However, twelve of the papers (35%) focused specifically on agri-data sharing and in this review are referred to as “the main data sharing studies”.

The published studies included: 10 papers from North America; 9 from Europe; 8 from Oceania; 3 from Africa; 2 from Asia; 1 from South America, and 1 conducted world-wide. Australia and the United States of America were the countries with the largest number of articles (24% and 21% of articles, respectively). Five of the twelve main data sharing studies (42%) examined perspectives on agricultural data sharing in Australia. Nearly 90% of the papers were journal articles, with only four conference papers included.

The studies included the perspective of farmers (~80% of studies), agronomists, technology providers, government, and researchers. All the main data sharing studies included the perspective of farmers. The two most common methodologies used for gathering stakeholder insights were interviews (32% of studies) and surveys (29%). The main data sharing studies centred on farmers’ perspectives of the benefits and risks of data sharing, data governance, and willingness to engage in data sharing.

3.2. Overview of factors affecting agricultural data sharing

Factors influencing the willingness and ability to participate in agricultural data sharing were identified across socio-economic, systemic, technical, and legal categories. Socio-economic factors encompass the social and economic realities that influence stakeholders’ decisions to engage in activities (Chisenga, 2015). Systemic factors, operating at the agri-chain level, create feedback loops that impact stakeholders’ decisions (Gemtou et al., 2024). Technical factors are related to technological challenges or solutions, and legal factors are shaped by regulations and policies. The most prominent drivers for agri-data sharing discussed were the socio-economic (65% of papers) and systemic factors (59% of papers; Figure 1). This result was emphasised in the main data sharing papers: 100% of the twelve papers discussed socio-economic enablers and 67% discussed systemic ones. Technical factors were the most frequently referenced barriers to data sharing, discussed in 68% of the studies (Figure 1). In the subset of main data sharing studies, systemic and legal barriers were the most prevalent, both in 75% of the studies.

Figure 1. Prominence of factors identified as influencing agri-data sharing. Light blue denotes main data sharing studies.

3.3. Sub-categorisation of factors

Within the four main categories, sub-categories were created based on findings from the literature. Table 1 includes the two most prominent sub-categories identified under each main category and examples found in the literature. Data governance is a complex and overarching topic, and its different aspects were allocated to the technical and legal categories. Discussions around data privacy and security were recorded within technical; while discussions of data ownership and rights of use were grouped as ‘data sovereignty’ and included in the legal category. The papers were not restricted to only one categorisation, as they could include references to multiple main and sub-categories. The percentage of papers in which the sub-category was discussed are included in Table 1 in brackets.

Table 1. Examples of the most prominent drivers and barriers of agri-data sharing identified in each category. The number in brackets is the percentage of articles (n=34) in which the factor was discussed.

Driver category & sub-category examples	Barrier category & sub-category examples
<p><u><i>Socio-economic drivers</i></u> Knowledge gain (38%) Informed decision-making; risk management; improved farm production</p> <p>Awareness of data sharing (26%) Clear understanding of value proposition</p>	<p><u><i>Socio-economic barriers</i></u> Lack of knowledge about data sharing (26%) Unclear about data benefits, data use, value of data, return on investment</p> <p>Required investment (12%) Time, money, and training needed</p>
<p><u><i>Systemic drivers</i></u> Trust and relationship building (29%) Use of existing trusting relationships</p> <p>Collaboration across agri-value chain (29%) Sharing knowledge for the common good; supply chain efficiencies; enhanced marketability</p>	<p><u><i>Systemic barriers</i></u> Lack of trust between stakeholders (35%) Unknown fate of data and who will benefit; exposure to competition</p> <p>Power imbalance and data misuse (29%) Fear of data used to influence market; farmers at mercy of technology providers</p>
<p><u><i>Technical drivers</i></u> Practical usage (21%) Ease-of-use of interface; data collection linked to farm realities; data storage & access</p> <p>Improved technologies (15%) New technologies; improved data analysis and modeling</p>	<p><u><i>Technical barriers</i></u> Privacy and security (53%) Lack of privacy and cybersecurity protection; complexity of personal/non-personal data</p> <p>Interoperability (24%) Incompatibilities; restricted data exchange; lack of transferability; data ‘lock-in’</p>
<p><u><i>Legal drivers</i></u> Data sovereignty (26%) Clarity and/or policy of data ownership and rights of use; transparency about data sharing licenses</p> <p>Beneficial policies and incentives (21%) Government incentives; CAP alignment; ease of administrative burden</p>	<p><u><i>Legal barriers</i></u> Lack of data sovereignty (41%) Lack of clarity for data ownership and rights of data use; lack of transparency in policies</p> <p>Harmful policies and regulations (15%) Compliance and regulations for data sharing; restrictive policies on data sharing</p>

3.4. Drivers of agri-data sharing

Identification of the most prominent drivers found in research studies can help inform future strategies aimed at promoting the benefits of agri-data sharing. While socio-economic factors emerged as the most prominent overall category of drivers, we also identified specific drivers discussed in the literature.

3.4.1. Socio-economic drivers

The perceived knowledge gain when sharing agricultural data was the most prominent driver identified across all papers (Table 3). Benefits related to knowledge gain, such as improved decision-making and risk management (Jakku et al., 2019; Newton et al., 2020; Regan, 2019), were discussed in 38% of all papers and

50% of the main data sharing papers, highlighting its importance from the farmer perspective. Discussions highlighted how farmers valued access to individual and pooled data for better opportunities and risk mitigation. Aggregated data could help address climate and market uncertainties, reduce inputs, improve crop quality, and increase efficiency and economic gain (McCarthy et al., 2023; Thompson et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024). Other agri-data sharing research projects have identified optimised production and risk management, tailored farming recommendations, and increased quality and quantity of products as key drivers for sharing data (van der Burg et al., 2020; Giesbers & Adema, 2021).

For these perceived benefits to drive interest in data sharing, farmers must understand the value proposition of agri-data sharing. The second most frequent enabler was individual awareness of the risks and benefits of sharing agricultural data (Table 3). This clear understanding was highlighted in seven of the twelve main data sharing studies as a prerequisite for agri-data sharing (Brown et al., 2023; Charvát et al., 2021; Wiseman et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2021).

3.4.2. Systemic drivers

Building trust in relationships and collaboration across the agri-value chain work hand-in-hand and were the two most frequently discussed systemic drivers for sharing agricultural data (Table 1). Aggregate data was viewed as beneficial for industry decision-making to optimise supply chain logistics and improve market projections (Jakku et al., 2019). Stakeholders saw the potential of using larger datasets for the common good of the industry, either by exchanging knowledge and sharing insights, or enhancing marketability of a sector (Boisier et al., 2021; Charvát et al., 2021; Eastwood et al., 2012; McCarthy et al., 2023). Stakeholders in Australia envisioned product traceability creating niche markets to meet consumer demands (Jakku et al., 2019), and data sharing in Ireland was viewed as a means of presenting a positive public image of the agricultural sector (Brown et al., 2023).

For the collaborative benefits of data sharing to be realised, trust and relationship building is required. The importance of involving stakeholder groups in the data sharing process that were already trusted partners of farmers was emphasised in the research. Farmers were most willing to share their data with researchers or other farmers, and least likely to share with the government (McCarthy et al., 2023; Turland & Slade, 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). As found in the wider literature, farmers' willingness to share data is influenced by who the data will be shared with, who they will be working with, and how much they trust this stakeholder group (Amiri-Zarandi et al., 2022; Eastwood et al., 2023).

3.4.3. Technical drivers

The technical drivers discussed most frequently in the papers were factors that improved the practicalities of data sharing, such as ease of use and increased data storage (Table 1). User-friendly interfaces were a significant enabler for data collection based on farmer surveys (Jerhamre et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2024). Incorporating data collection into farmers' normal activities further enhanced their willingness, such as linking data collection to a regular farm activity (Eastwood et al., 2012) or using a data platform that was integrated into an existing farm management software (Schambow et al., 2022).

The second most prominent technical driver were new technologies that spur innovation across the agri-sector (Table 1). Examples included higher-quality weather and crop models coupled with data analysis (Newton et al., 2020) and the possibilities from new technologies like artificial intelligence (Alexander et al., 2024). This optimistic outlook of innovative technologies is supported by other literature reviews related to big data and smart farming (Abbasi et al., 2022; Akella et al., 2023).

3.4.4. Legal drivers

In the legal category, it was widely reported that clarification of data ownership and transparent data use licenses were a critical incentive for agri-data sharing (Brown et al., 2023; Charvát et al., 2021; Idowu et al., 2023; McCarthy et al., 2023; van der Burg et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). This is supported by discussions in the wider literature of legal frameworks that tackle accountability and responsibility within the data-sharing chain (Amiri-Zarandi et al., 2022; Eastwood et al., 2023). While codes of conduct have been developed to help protect farmers' rights and make data sharing more transparent, these codes of conduct are voluntary, including the European Union Code of Conduct on Agricultural Data Sharing by Contractual Agreement (van der Burg et al., 2021).

Beneficial governmental policies and incentives were discussed as encouragements of data sharing (Jerhamre et al., 2022), especially if data aggregation and analysis support was provided (Newton et al.,

2020). Sharing data digitally was also viewed as a way to decrease the administrative burden for demonstrating compliance with regulations or in applying for government subsidies (Kutter et al., 2011; Reissig et al., 2022).

3.5. Barriers of agri-data sharing

The main barriers of agricultural data sharing identified in the papers were often the “lack” of the associated driver (Table 1). As a main category, technical factors were discussed in 68% of all papers and were the most prominent barriers to agri-data sharing.

3.5.1. Socio-economic barriers

Lack of knowledge about the benefits or use of shared data was by far the most significant socio-economic obstacle for sharing farm data (Table 1). Almost 60% of the main data sharing papers referenced lack of clarity about the value, applicability, or benefit of data to farmers as a serious deterrent for sharing agri-data (Jakku et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2022). Although much less prevalent, the required investment of time and money to adopt a technology and learn new skills was referenced in 17% of the papers. When the benefits of data sharing are not clear, farmers are less likely to invest in a new practice. In these instances, the farmer may lose interest in data-gathering technologies that are not required because the risks outweigh the unclear benefits (Brown et al., 2023; Regan, 2019). In contrast to reviews on the adoption of smart farming practices (Fragomeli et al., 2024; Gemtoui et al., 2024), farm and farmer characteristics such as farm size, age, and education were not identified as prominent barriers to agri-data sharing in our review.

3.5.2. Systemic barriers

Lack of trust between stakeholders was the most prominent systemic barrier, identified in 35% of the papers (Table 1). Uncertainty and fear about the fate of data generated once it left the farm was reported by farmers, resulting in mistrust towards data aggregators. The sense of mistrust was ascribed to not knowing how data would be used, who would benefit from their data, and the repercussions with competitors (Alexander et al., 2024; Brown et al., 2023; Charvát et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). These concerns were further exacerbated by the complex power imbalance that exists across the agri-value chain and fear of data being misused.

Trust in data sharing and fear of misuse was dependent on who the data was shared with. For example, growers were found to be least willing to share data with government for fear of selective data being used to misrepresent an industry or in the creation of unjust policies (Brown et al., 2023; Wiseman et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2021). Farmers were also concerned that agriculture companies could adjust prices based on aggregated farm input or output data (Brown et al., 2023). The imbalance in operation size, bargaining power, data knowledge, and technology access between individual farmers and agricultural technology providers has left farmers at the mercy of large technology providers (Boisier et al., 2021; Charvát et al., 2021). Unbalanced power relationships and lack of trust are barriers that have been identified in wider research related to data-driven agriculture (Abbasi et al., 2022; Atik, 2023; Kamilaris et al., 2017; Klerkx et al., 2019). In exploring the creation of shared data spaces, Eastwood et al. (2023) and Šestak and Copot (2023) identified mistrust in the data-sharing process as a serious and complex obstacle.

3.5.3. Technical barriers

The challenge surrounding data privacy and cybersecurity was the most prominent barrier identified in the study, referenced in 53% of all papers and 58% of the main data sharing studies (Table 1). From the farmers' perspective, there was a lack of confidence and trust that their privacy and cybersecurity would be maintained across the data-sharing chain (e.g., Bach et al., 2020; Drewry et al., 2019; Ibrahim et al., 2020; Jakku et al., 2019). The difficulty in separating ‘personal’ from ‘non-personal’ data within farm production data exacerbated this concern (Brown et al., 2023). The prominence of security and data privacy as challenges is supported in technical reviews on the use of big data in agriculture and data sharing obstacles (Amiri-Zarandi et al., 2022; Kamilaris et al., 2017; Wolfert et al., 2017).

The second most prominent technical challenge was data interoperability, although it was discussed less frequently in the main data sharing studies (17%). Because agricultural data is collected and stored in different formats, it is very difficult to integrate datasets. Farmers referred to both the incompatibility between systems on-farm (machinery) and between different service providers or databases as significant technical obstacles for sharing data (Bach et al., 2020; Jakku et al., 2019; Jerhamre et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2024).

The inability to transfer datasets between providers or equipment manufacturers is discussed in the wider literature as resulting in restricted data exchange and farmers being ‘locked-in’ with the first technology provider they sign on with (Atik, 2023; Kosior, 2020).

3.5.4. Legal barriers

The lack of clarity and assurance on data ownership, data use, and transfer rights (together termed ‘data sovereignty’) was the most significant legal barrier for engaging in data sharing (Table 1). Studies discussed farmers’ desires for data ownership rights and transparency in data use agreements but highlighted the complexity of ‘data ownership’ vs ‘data use’ (Atik, 2023; van der Burg et al., 2021). It is possible for farmers to own their data, but have very little control over its use, since data use is part of the license agreement that farmers need to sign to use smart farming technologies (Wiseman et al., 2019). The research indicates that farmers are often unaware of, or do not understand the contracts they sign and have limited trust in protection guidelines (Gabriel, 2023; Wiseman et al., 2019). Other studies from the wider literature highlight that the primary challenge in agri-data sharing is the lack of protection or regulations regarding data sovereignty (Giesbers & Adema, 2021; McGrath et al., 2023).

Potential regulatory repercussions were discussed in 12% of the studies as a reason to now share data. These included concerns of harmful policies based on selective data (Brown et al., 2023) or restrictive data-driven regulations (McCarthy et al., 2023; Regan, 2019; Schambow et al., 2022).

3.6. Intersection of drivers and barriers

The socio-technical complexity of data sharing makes it difficult to separate the factors impacting data-sharing willingness (Eastwood et al., 2023). Promoting data sharing by highlighting knowledge benefits (socio-economic driver) requires trusted relationships and clear communication of risks and benefits (systemic drivers), privacy assurance (technical driver), and clarity on data usage rights (legal driver). Data privacy, a technical barrier, is tied to socio-economic concerns about data misuse (systemic barrier) and harmful regulations (legal barrier). Farmers worry about data privacy but often lack understanding of service agreements due to poor communication and policy transparency (systemic and legal barriers).

3.7. Future work

To enhance data sharing in agriculture, trust needs to be addressed from various perspectives. Literature suggests that clarifying data sharing benefits across stakeholder groups, leveraging existing trusted relationships, involving farmers in technology research and data governance, and transparent data sharing policies can foster trust (Raturi et al., 2022; van der Burg et al., 2021). However, concrete strategies to achieve these goals are lacking. Given that only twelve studies in this review specifically addressed agri-data sharing, there is a clear need for more stakeholder-centred research. The next step is to link the review’s findings with practical research in Europe that is context-specific. The aim should be to develop a framework and strategy that leverages the prominent data-sharing enablers to overcome significant barriers. The benefits of agri-data sharing must be promoted in a way that encourages the adoption of data-gathering technologies as a means of enhancing farm viability.

4. Conclusions

The factors influencing stakeholders’ motivation and capability to share agri-data into socio-economic, systemic, technical, and legal categories. Key enablers included perceived knowledge gain (socio-economic), collaborative benefits and building trust (systemic), clarity surrounding data sovereignty (legal), and improving the practicalities of data sharing (technical). The most significant barrier was the concern of maintaining data privacy and cybersecurity (technical), followed by unclear data ownership and rights of use (legal), trust issues (systemic), and a lack of understanding data sharing benefits and risks (socio-economic). This review stresses the complexity and interconnected nature of these factors and emphasises the need for balanced policies that encourage innovation while protecting farmers’ interests. The classification of factors conducted in this review will help guide future research in promoting feasible data-sharing practices.

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